

ANALYSIS OF DEFORMATION OF RUBBER COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

The deformation of rubber composite material is analysed numerically with the Mooney-Rivlin type strain energy function and the distributions of stress and strain in the material are calculated. The finite element method and two plane models of inhomogeneous material are used for the numerical simulation. Rectangular regions and elliptic inclusions are assumed to be placed regularly in the models. The applied stress is assumed to be uniaxial tension under the plane stress condition. In order to express the mode of deformation quantitatively, a parameter called constraint ratio is defined. The constraint ratio is equal to 0 for the constant strain deformation, while it is equal to 1 for the constant stress deformation. It is found that the mode of deformation is similar to the constant strain mode as the shape of the inhomogeneous region becomes slender in the stress direction. The mutual constraint between the inhomogeneous regions is weaker for the material with Mooney-Rivlin type constitutive relation than that with the commonly used linear elastic stress-strain relation, which results from the lack of the resistance for shear deformation in Mooney-Rivlin relation.

KEYWORDS : Composites ; Rubber ; Finite Element Analysis ; Nonlinear ; Uniaxial Loading.

1. INTRODUCTION

Non-uniform distribution of stress and strain is produced in an inhomogeneous material after deformation. Inhomogeneity of various sizes exists in most engineering rubber materials, because various elements are usually added. Furthermore, material design has been developed in recent years. Artificial composite materials having special characteristics are made such as polymer blends or fiber reinforcement. The inhomogeneity are expected to affect on various aspects of deformation of engineering materials. Hence, it is important to study the fundamental characteristics of microscopic deformation behaviour or the distribution of stress and strain in inhomogeneous materials⁽¹⁾.

Inhomogeneous material is considered as a body having different stress-strain relation or constitutive equation at each point of the body. In the present study, two simple geometrical models are considered as the representatives of rubber composite materials. The first model is composed of regularly distributed rectangular regions with different elastic constants. The second model is regularly distributed elliptic inclusions in a matrix. Numerical simulation with finite element method is performed and fundamental characteristics of the deformation behaviour is discussed.

2. METHOD OF CALCULATION

In order to make simplified analysis of finite deformation of rubber, the finite element program based on the small deformation elasticity is modified⁽²⁾. The constitutive equation derived from strain energy function is adopted to analyse the deformation of rubber composite.

2.1 Constitutive Equation for Rubber The strain energy function W is expressed in terms of the three invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 ⁽³⁾ in general.

$$W(I_1, I_2, I_3)$$

The large deformation of rubber is usually expressed with the extension-ratio λ .

$$\lambda = l / l_0, \quad (1)$$

where l_0 and l are the initial length and the length after deformation, respectively. The three invariants for the finite deformation are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
I_1 &= \lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 + \lambda_{33}^2 \\
I_2 &= \lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2 \lambda_{33}^2 + \lambda_{33}^2 \lambda_{11}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4 - \lambda_{23}^4 - \lambda_{31}^4 \\
I_3 &= \lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 \lambda_{33}^2 + 2\lambda_{12}^2 \lambda_{23}^2 \lambda_{31}^2 - \lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{23}^4 \\
&\quad - \lambda_{22}^2 \lambda_{31}^4 - \lambda_{33}^2 \lambda_{12}^4
\end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

The component of stress σ_{ij} ($i, j=1, 2, 3$) is given by differentiating the strain energy function W with respect to the corresponding component λ_{ij} of the extension-ratio⁽³⁾.

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial \lambda_{ij}} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_1} \frac{\partial I_1}{\partial \lambda_{ij}} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_2} \frac{\partial I_2}{\partial \lambda_{ij}} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial I_3} \frac{\partial I_3}{\partial \lambda_{ij}} \tag{3}$$

Now, we consider the plane problem and assume that the direction 3 is in the normal direction to the plane.

$$\sigma_{33} = \sigma_{23} = \sigma_{31} = 0, \quad \lambda_{23} = \lambda_{31} = 0 \tag{4}$$

When the incompressibility of rubber is assumed, $I_3 = 1$. Then, from the third equation of Eq. (2), we have

$$\lambda_{33}^2 = 1 / (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4) \tag{5}$$

In the present study, the well-known Mooney-Rivlin function is adopted as the strain energy function.

$$W = \phi (I_1 - 3) / 2 + \psi (I_2 - 3) / 2 \tag{6}$$

where ϕ and ψ are the material constants. From Eq.(6), we have

$$\partial W / \partial I_1 = \phi / 2, \quad \partial W / \partial I_2 = \psi / 2 \tag{7}$$

Substituting Eqs. (2),(4)-(7) into Eq. (3), the stress components are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma_{11} &= \frac{\lambda_{11}}{(\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2} [\{ (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2 - \lambda_{22}^2 \} \phi \\
&\quad + \{ \lambda_{22}^2 (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2 - \lambda_{12}^4 - \lambda_{22}^4 \} \psi] \\
\sigma_{22} &= \frac{\lambda_{22}}{(\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2} [\{ (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2 - \lambda_{11}^2 \} \phi \\
&\quad + \{ \lambda_{11}^2 (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2 - \lambda_{12}^4 - \lambda_{11}^4 \} \psi] \tag{8} \\
\sigma_{12} &= \frac{2\lambda_{12}^3}{(\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2} [\phi - \{ (\lambda_{11}^2 \lambda_{22}^2 - \lambda_{12}^4)^2 \\
&\quad - (\lambda_{11}^2 + \lambda_{22}^2) \} \psi]
\end{aligned}$$

2.2 Stress-Strain-Displacement Relations The stress-strain relation under the plane stress is expressed with the matrix form as follows.

$$\{\sigma\} = [D] \{\lambda\} \tag{9}$$

The components of the matrix $[D]$ are obtained by differentiating the stress components [Eq. (8)] with respect to the components of strain.

In the finite element formulation for small strain, the relation between strain ϵ and deformation d is given with matrix form as follows⁽⁴⁾.

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B]\{d\} \tag{10}$$

where $[B]$ is the matrix obtained from the strain-deformation relation. When the extension-ratio λ [Eq. (1)] is adopted for rubber, it is possible to use the following relation.

$$[B'] = \{\lambda\}[B] \tag{11}$$

In order to examine the accuracy of the finite element calculation, the analytical solution of uniaxial tension of homogeneous body is obtained. Substituting $\sigma_{22} = \sigma_{12} = 0$ into Eq. (8), we have $\lambda_{12} = 0$. As $\lambda_{22} = \lambda_{33}$, we have $\lambda_{22} = 1 / \sqrt{\lambda_{11}}$ from the condition of volume constancy $\lambda_{11} = \lambda_{22} = \lambda_{33} = 1$. Thus, the analytical solution for uniaxial tension is given by

$$\sigma_{11} = (\lambda_{11} - 1 / \lambda_{11}^2) (\phi + \psi / \lambda_{11}) \tag{12}$$

2.3 Model of Composite

Figure 1 shows plane models of rubber composites used in the present finite element simulation. The first model is composed of regularly placed rectangular regions having two kinds of Young's moduli shown with + and - signs in Figure 1(a). The second model is composed of inclusions regularly placed in a matrix as shown in Figure 1(b). Owing to the symmetry of the geometrical configuration, the whole area of the respective models is represented with the area OACB and the boundaries of the area remain straight after deformation. In the following, the applied stress is assumed to be uniaxial tension in 1- or x-direction and constant displacement is given for each side of the boundaries OACB. The initial aspect ratio R_0 and the aspect ratio R after

FIGURE 1. Plane model of inhomogeneous material

deformation of the regions OACB are defined respectively by

$$R = b / a \quad , \quad R_0 = b_0 / a_0 \quad (13)$$

where a and b are the lengths of the regions in 1(x)- and 2(y)-directions (OA and OB in Figure 1), respectively. a_0 and b_0 are the initial values. The effect of the initial aspect ratio R_0 on the deformation behaviour of the composite models is studied. For the finite element calculation, the area OACB is divided into 576 triangular constant strain elements with 313 nodes for the first model [Figure 1(a)], while it is divided into 252 triangular elements with 143 nodes for the second model [Figure 1(b)].

2.4 Numerical Calculation The large deformation of non-linear rubber material is analysed by repeated finite element calculation with small deformation step. The displacement of the nodes is taken into account at every deformation step. The thickness of the elements is also adjusted considering the incompressibility at every step.

It is necessary to determine the boundary displacement in 2(y)-direction corresponding to the uniaxial load applied in 1(x)-direction. The increment $\Delta \lambda_y$ of the extension-ratio in y-direction is given from the increment $\Delta \lambda_x$ in x-direction as follows.

$$\Delta \lambda_y = \sqrt{1 / (\lambda_x + \Delta \lambda_x)} - \lambda_y \quad (14)$$

The material constants in Mooney-Rivlin function are assumed to be $\psi_+ = \psi_I = 0.75$ (MPa) for the + region or the inclusion and $\psi_- = \psi_M = 0.25$ (MPa) for the - region or the matrix. The parameter ϕ is constant $\phi = 1.0$ (MPa) throughout the models.

In order to examine the accuracy of numerical calculation, the numerical results for the uniaxial tension of homogeneous body are compared with the analytical solution. After the extension of $\lambda_x = 3$, the error of the numerical calculation is 0.75% and 0.075% for the increments $\Delta \lambda_x = 0.01$ and 0.001, respectively. Hence, the increment $\Delta \lambda_x = 0.001$ is adopted in the following calculation.

2.5 Constraint Ratio In order to express the mode of deformation of inhomogeneous materials quantitatively, the constraint ratio η is defined by

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \eta &= \frac{\Delta \lambda}{(\Delta \lambda)_{max}} = \frac{\tilde{K}}{\tilde{K} - K} \\ \Delta \lambda &= \lambda - \tilde{\lambda} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

where λ is the extension-ratio at an arbitrary point in a body and $\tilde{\lambda}$ is the mean value of λ for the whole material. $(\Delta\lambda)_{\max}$ is the value of $\Delta\lambda$ under the constant stress condition as shown in Figure 2. \tilde{K} is the inclination of the averaged stress-strain relation for the whole material. K' is the inclination of the line connecting the points \circ and \bullet in Figure 3. From Eq. (15), we have

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \eta = 0 : \text{ constant strain} \\ \eta = 1 : \text{ constant stress} \end{array} \right\} \quad (16)$$

3. RESULT OF CALCULATION AND DISCUSSION

Figures 3(a)-(c) show the numerical results of deformation behaviour of the rectangular inhomogeneous model for the initial aspect ratios $R_0 = 0.1, 1.0$ and 10.0 , respectively. The marks \circ and \bullet in Figure 3 show the change in the mean values of stress and extension-ratio for the two different inhomogeneous regions. The solid lines are the analytical solution given by Eq. (12) under the uniaxial stress for the respective regions with different Young's modulus [Figure 1(a)]. The marks \square in Figure 3 show the change in the aspect ratio R after deformation.

The mark \blacksquare in Figure 3 represents the inclination K' of the line connecting the marks \circ and \bullet . When the inclination is small, the deformation mode is similar to the constant stress mode. Meanwhile, when the inclination is large, the deformation is similar to the constant strain mode. It is seen from Figure 3 that the deformation mode is similar to that under the constant strain when the initial aspect ratio R_0 is small, that is, when the shape of inhomogeneous regions is slender in the tensile direction. The deformation mode is affected by the mutual restriction of deformation. Therefore, the respective lengths of the boundaries FG and HI shown in Figure 1(a) or the aspect ratio $R = b/a$ is important⁽¹⁾. When the shape of inhomogeneous regions is slender in the loading direction, the mode of deformation becomes similar to that under constant strain and the value of Young's modulus for the whole material increases⁽⁵⁾.

Although the inclination K' represents the mode of deformation of composite body, it is dependent on the stress-strain curve. Hence, another dimensionless parameter called constraint ratio η is calculated with Eq. (15) and the mean value of η for the composites is shown with the mark \blacksquare in Figure 3.

Figures 4(a) shows the distributions of stress σ_x and strain λ_x along the loading direction [along OA in Figure 1(a)]. Figures 4(b) and (c) show the distributions along perpendicular direction to the loading direction [along OB in Figure 1(a)]. Figures 4(a) and (b) are the results for the extension-ratio $\lambda_x = 2.0$. Figure 4(c) is for small deformation

FIGURE 2. Definition of constraint ratio η on stress-extension-ratio diagram

(a) $R_0 = 0.1$

(b) $R_0 = 1.0$

(c) $R_0 = 10.0$

FIGURE 3. Stress-strain relation of rubber composite model with rectangular inhomogeneous regions [$\phi = 1.0$ (MPa), Δ and \blacktriangle show result for $D_{33} = (D_{11} - D_{12})/2$]

$\lambda_x = 1.01$. The distributions of stress and strain for the initial aspect ratios $R_0 = 0.05, 0.1, 1.0$ and 10.0 are shown in Figure 4. The stress is continuous along OA as shown in Figure 4(a), while the strain is continuous along OB as shown in Figure 4(b)⁽¹⁾. It is also seen from the comparison of Figures 4(a) and (c) that the deformation mode changes toward the constant strain mode with the increase of extension-ratio λ . The above mentioned deformation mode is recognized in the change of η with R_0 and λ in Figure 3. The value of constraint ratio η becomes smaller with the tensile deformation, which results from the decrease of the aspect ratio R with the increase of extension-ratio.

(a) Along OA ($\lambda_x = 2.0$)

(b) Along OB ($\lambda_x = 2.0$)

(c) Along OB ($\lambda_x = 1.01$)

FIGURE 4. Distribution of stress σ_x and extension-ratio λ_x along OA or OB in Figure 1(a)

The deformation of inhomogeneous Mooney-Rivlin material resembles to that of small deformation linear elastic material. There are, however, some discrepancies between them. As an example, we consider the component D_{33} in [D] matrix in the stress-strain relation.

$$\{\sigma\} = [D] \{\epsilon\} \quad (17)$$

For the plane stress, [D] matrix for the linear elasticity is given by⁽⁴⁾

$$[D] = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \nu & 0 \\ \nu & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & (1-\nu)/2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

where E and ν are Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, respectively. From Eq. (18), we have

$$D_{33} = (D_{11} - D_{12})/2 \quad (19)$$

which generally is not zero. On the hand, the initial value of D_{33} for Mooney-Rivlin material under uniaxial tension is zero, because $\lambda_{12} = 0$ at the initial state.

The results shown with the marks \triangle and \blacktriangle in Figure 3(b) are the deformation behaviour of Mooney-Rivlin material where non-zero value of D_{33} is artificially given from the beginning according to Eq. (19)⁽²⁾. The results show that the inclination of the line connecting the marks \triangle and \blacktriangle is larger than that connecting the marks \circ and \bullet for the standard Mooney-Rivlin material. This implies that the deformation of Mooney-Rivlin material is closer to the constant stress mode than the deformation of the linear elastic material, because of the lack of shear resistance ($D_{33}=0$).

Figure 5 shows the calculated results for the spherical inclusions imbedded in matrix ($R_0=1$), where the different values of the constant ψ in Mooney-Rivlin equation is given in inclusion and matrix. The result shown in Figure 5 is similar to that shown in Figure 3(b) for $R_0=1$. The value of constraint ratio η , however, is slightly smaller for the inclusion model than for the rectangular model⁽⁵⁾.

4. CONCLUSION

In order to analyse the deformation behaviour of rubber composite material, the stress-strain relation is derived from Mooney-Rivlin type strain energy function and is incorporated into the finite element formulation. Two models of inhomogeneous material are adopted; one is composed of rectangular regions having different Young's moduli and the

other has inclusions regularly imbeded in matrix. The results obtained are summarized as follows.

(1) When the shape of inhomogeneous region is slender in the stress direction, the deformation mode becomes close to that under the constant strain. This results from the mutual restriction of deformation on the both sides of the boundaries between the regions.

(2) The Mooney-Rivlin material deforms in a mode closer to the constant stress than the usual small-strain linear elastic body, which is related to the weak shear resistance between the neighbouring inhomogeneous regions for Mooney-Rivlin material.

(3) A non-dimensional parameter called constraint ratio is defined for the non-linear elastic deformation, which seems to represent the deformation mode of rubber composite quantitatively.

FIGURE 5. Stress-extension-ratio relation of rubber composite material with inclusions [$R_0=1.0$, $\phi=1.0$ (MPa)]

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